

On Dynamics of Cubic Stochastic Operators

A. Doniyorov¹

¹ Karshi state university Department of Mathematical analysis and differential equations

Abstract:

In this paper, we consider a class of cubic stochastic operators defined on a finite-dimensional simplex. Namely, cubic stochastic operators that have the form of a product of three linear operators defined on a simplex.

Keywords: Cubic stochastic operator, simplex, fixed point, limit point.

Introduction

There are many systems which are described by nonlinear operators. A quadratic stochastic operator (QSO) is one of the simplest nonlinear cases.

Let $E = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be a finite set and the set of all probability distribution on E

$$S^{m-1} = \{x = (x_1, \dots, x_m) \in \mathbb{R}^m: x_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^m x_i = 1\} \quad (1)$$

be the $(m-1)$ -dimensional simplex. A QSO is a mapping defined as $V: S^{m-1} \rightarrow S^{m-1}$ of the simplex into itself, of the form $V(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}' \in S^{m-1}$, where

$$x'_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^m P_{ij,k} x_i x_j, \quad k \in E, \quad (2)$$

and the coefficients $P_{ij,k}$ satisfy

$$P_{ij,k} = P_{ji,k} \geq 0, \quad \sum_{k=1}^m P_{ij,k} = 1 \text{ for all } i, j \in E. \quad (3)$$

The trajectory (orbit) $\{\mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}_{n \geq 0}$, of V for an initial value $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in S^{m-1}$ is defined by

$$\mathbf{x}^{(n+1)} = V(\mathbf{x}^{(n)}) = V^{(n+1)}(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

One of the main problems in mathematical biology is to study the asymptotic behavior of the trajectories. This problem was solved completely for the Volterra QSO.

For a given $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in S^{m-1}$, the trajectory $\{\mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}_{n \geq 0}$ of initial point $\mathbf{x}^{(0)}$ under action of CSO (8) is defined by $\mathbf{x}^{(n+1)} = W(\mathbf{x}^{(n)})$, where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}^{(0)}$. Denote by $\omega(\mathbf{x}^{(0)})$ the set of limit points of the trajectory $\{\mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$. Since $\{\mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}_{n=0}^{\infty} \subset S^{m-1}$ and S^{m-1} is a compact set, it follows that $\omega(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) \neq \emptyset$. If $\omega(\mathbf{x}^{(0)})$ consists of a single point, then the trajectory converges and $\omega(\mathbf{x}^{(0)})$ is a fixed point of the operator W . A point $\mathbf{x} \in S^{m-1}$ is called a fixed of the W if $W(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}$. Denote by $\text{Fix}(W)$ the set of all fixed points of the operator W , i.e.

$$\text{Fix}(W) = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^{m-1} : W(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}\}.$$

Let $DW(\mathbf{x}^*) = (\partial W_i / \partial x_j)(\mathbf{x}^*)$ be a Jacobian of W at the point $\mathbf{x}^*$.

We consider CSO (2), (3) with additional condition

$$P_{ijk,l} = a_{il} b_{jl} c_{kl}, \text{ for all } i, j, k, l \in E, \quad (7)$$

where $a_{il}, b_{jl}, c_{kl} \in \mathbb{R}$ entries of matrices $A = (a_{il})$, $B = (b_{jl})$ and $C = (c_{kl})$ such that the conditions (3) are satisfied for the coefficients (7).

Then the CSO W corresponding to the coefficients (7) has the form

$$x'_l = (W(\mathbf{x}))_l = (A(\mathbf{x}))_l (B(\mathbf{x}))_l (C(\mathbf{x}))_l \quad (8)$$

where $(A(\mathbf{x}))_l = \sum_{i=1}^m a_{il} x_i$, $(B(\mathbf{x}))_l = \sum_{j=1}^m b_{jl} x_j$ and $(C(\mathbf{x}))_l = \sum_{k=1}^m c_{kl} x_k$.

Definition 5. The CSO (12) is called separable cubic stochastic operator (SCSO).

Let us consider the following matrices:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 + \frac{a}{2} \\ 1 - a & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 - a & 1 \end{pmatrix}, C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 + a & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 + a \\ 1 - \frac{a}{2} & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where $a \in [-1, 1]$.

Then corresponding SCSO $W : S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ is:

$$W : \begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1 (x_1 + (1 - a)x_2 + x_3) \left(x_1 + x_2 + \left(1 - \frac{a}{2}\right)x_3 \right), \\ x'_2 = x_2 (x_1 + x_2 + (1 - a)x_3) \left((1 + a)x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \right), \\ x'_3 = x_3 \left(\left(1 + \frac{a}{2}\right)x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \right) \left(x_1 + (1 + a)x_2 + x_3 \right). \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Using the equation $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 1$ we rewrite the operator (10) as follows

$$W : \begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1 (1 - ax_2) \left(1 - \frac{a}{2}x_3 \right), \\ x'_2 = x_2 (1 - ax_3) (1 + ax_1), \\ x'_3 = x_3 \left(1 + \frac{a}{2}x_1 \right) (1 + ax_2). \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Evidently, that if $a = 0$ the SCSO (11) is the identity map. For this in the below, we consider the case when $a \neq 0$.

Let a face of the simplex S^2 be the set $\Gamma_\alpha = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_i = 0, i \notin \alpha \subset \{1, 2, 3\}\}$.

Let the set $\text{int } S^2 = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_1 x_2 x_3 > 0\}$ and let the set $\partial S^2 = S^2 \setminus \text{int } S^2$ be the interior and the boundary of the simplex S^2 , respectively. Let $\mathbf{e}_1 = (1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{e}_2 = (0, 1, 0)$, $\mathbf{e}_3 = (0, 0, 1)$ be the vertexes of the two-dimensional simplex.

Let $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in S^2$ be the initial point. Then the trajectory of $\mathbf{x}^{(0)}$ is denote by $\{\mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}_{n \geq 0}$ and is defined as $W(\mathbf{x}^{(n)}) = \mathbf{x}^{(n+1)}$ where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

Theorem 1. For the SCSO W (11), the following assertions true:

(i) If $a \in [-1, 0)$, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_2 & \text{if } \mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in \Gamma_{\{2,3\}} \setminus \{\mathbf{e}_3\}, \\ \mathbf{e}_1 & \text{if } \mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{2,3\}}. \end{cases}$$

(ii) If $a \in (0, 1]$, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_2 & \text{if } \mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in \Gamma_{\{1,2\}} \setminus \{\mathbf{e}_1\}, \\ \mathbf{e}_3 & \text{if } \mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{1,2\}}. \end{cases}$$

Proof: (i) If $a \in [-1, 0)$. Let $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = (0, x_2^{(0)}, x_3^{(0)}) \in \Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$. By Theorem 1, the face $\Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$ is an invariant set and the vertexes $\mathbf{e}_2$ and $\mathbf{e}_3$ are fixed points belonging to this face. For the SCSO W (11) is true $x_1^{(n)} = 0$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ at the face $\Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$. The restriction of the SCSO W (11) on the face $\Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$ has the form

$$\begin{cases} x_2' = x_2(x_2 + (1-a)x_3), \\ x_3' = x_3((1+a)x_2 + x_3). \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

From the first equation of (12), one has

$$x_2^{(n+1)} = x_2^{(n)}(1 - ax_3^{(n)}) \geq x_2^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, it follows that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_2^{(n)} = x_2^*$. Moreover, from the second equation of (12), one has

$$x_3^{(n+1)} = x_3^{(n)}(1 + ax_2^{(n)}) \leq x_3^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, it follows that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_3^{(n)} = x_3^*$. So there is the limit

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{x}^* = (0, x_2^*, x_3^*)$. Since $\mathbf{x}^*$ should be a fixed we get $\mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{e}_2$. That is, if $x_2^{(0)} > 0$ then we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{e}_2$ for any $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = \Gamma_{\{2,3\}} \setminus \{\mathbf{e}_3\}$.

Let $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$. Then, from the first equation of operator (12), one has

$$x_1^{(n+1)} = x_1^{(n)} \left(1 - \frac{a}{2} x_3^{(n)} \right) (1 - ax_2^{(n)}) \geq x_1^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

So we have that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_1^{(n)} = x_1^*$. Moreover, from the third equation of operator (12), one has

$$x_3^{(n+1)} = x_3^{(n)} \left(1 + \frac{a}{2} x_1^{(n)} \right) (1 + ax_2^{(n)}) \leq x_3^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, it follows that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_3^{(n)} = x_3^*$. Thus, using $x_1^{(n)} + x_2^{(n)} + x_3^{(n)} = 1$ we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_2^{(n)} = x_2^*$. So there is the limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{x}^* = (x_1^*, x_2^*, x_3^*)$. Since $\mathbf{x}^*$ should be a fixed point we get $\mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{e}_1$.

Consequently, we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{e}_1$ for any $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$.

(ii) If $a \in (0, 1]$. Let $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} \in \Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$. By Theorem 1, the face $\Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$ is an invariant set and the vertexes $\mathbf{e}_1$ and $\mathbf{e}_2$ are fixed points belonging to this face. The restriction of the SCSO W (20) on the face $\Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$ has the form

$$\begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1(x_1 + (1-a)x_2), \\ x'_2 = x_2((1+a)x_1 + x_2). \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Not that, for the SCSO W (13) is true $x_3^{(n)} = 0$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ at the face $\Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$. From the first equation of (13), one has

$$x_1^{(n+1)} = x_1^{(n)} (1 - ax_2^{(n)}) \leq x_1^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, it follows that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_1^{(n)} = x_1^*$. Moreover, from the second equation of (13), one has

$$x_2^{(n+1)} = x_2^{(n)} (1 + ax_1^{(n)}) \geq x_2^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

So we have that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_2^{(n)} = x_2^*$. Hence there is the limit

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{x}^* = (x_1^*, x_2^*, 0)$. Since $\mathbf{x}^*$ should be a fixed point we get $\mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{e}_2$. That is, if $x_2^{(0)} > 0$ then we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{e}_2$ for any $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = \Gamma_{\{1,2\}} \setminus \{\mathbf{e}_1\}$.

Let $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$. Then, from the first equation of operator (11), one has

$$x_1^{(n+1)} = x_1^{(n)} \left(1 - \frac{a}{2} x_3^{(n)} \right) (1 - ax_2^{(n)}) \leq x_1^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, it follows that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_1^{(n)} = x_1^*$. Moreover, from the third equation of operator (13), one has

$$x_3^{(n+1)} = x_3^{(n)} \left(1 + \frac{a}{2} x_1^{(n)} \right) (1 + ax_2^{(n)}) \geq x_3^{(n)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Hence one has that there exists the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_3^{(n)} = x_3^*$. Thus, using $x_1^{(n)} + x_2^{(n)} + x_3^{(n)} = 1$ we have

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_2^{(n)} = x_2^*$. So there is the limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{x}^* = (x_1^*, x_2^*, x_3^*)$. Since $\mathbf{x}^*$ should be a fixed point we get $\mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{e}_3$.

Consequently, we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W^n(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{e}_3$ for any $\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = S^2 \setminus \Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$.

The theorem is proved. $\square$

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